

YOUTH AND SPORT: PSYCHOLOGICAL BARRIERS IN THE SPORT OF HIGHER ACHIEVEMENTS

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Abstract: *In the article the contradictions of elite sport from the point of view of the personality of an athlete are analyzed. In modern conditions of development of society and civilization the tasks of elite and mass sport significantly differ that leads to absolutely various requirements in the field of physical, technical and psychological training of athletes. The special part is assigned to psychological training of athletes in which the central place is taken by development of the motivational sphere and formation of special personal qualities of the athlete. The psychological barriers arising in high-class athletes can serve as an obstacle on the way to achieving high results.*

Keywords— sport, elite sport, contradictions of elite sport, crises of sports career, identity of the athlete, psychological barrier.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern world, sport is an important sphere of public life, reflecting many areas of human activity and civilization: medicine, economics, politics, show business, high technologies in the manufacture of shells and equipment, etc. In order for an athlete to climb the podium, a well-coordinated work of a whole team of specialists is necessary: a coach, doctors, massage therapists, equipment developers and, of course, an athlete and his social environment - family, loved ones, friends, teammates and sports. When this, the requirements for the physical and psychological training of the athlete are constantly increasing, the athlete is under colossal pressing requirements and all kinds of difficulties and obstacles that must be constantly overcome.

The process of overcoming oneself and the situation can be both evolutionary and revolutionary (crisis) nature. From the point of view of G. Allport, "A crisis is a situation of emotional and mental stress that requires significant change ideas about the world and about yourself in a short period of time. Often, a similar revision representation entails changes in the structure of the personality. These changes can be worn as positive as well as negative. By definition, a person in crisis is not may remain the same; in other words, she is not managing to comprehend his current psycho-traumatic experience, operating with familiar, stereotyped categories, or use simple familiar models of adaptation" [8, p. 132].

2. MAIN PART

The athlete lives in some "detachment" from the real world, the surrounding world is limited by the training process, the team acts as a substitute for the family, and coaches,

psychologists, massage therapists - parents. This situation sometimes leads to the fact that the athlete feels very comfortable in

in the usual training environment and shows fairly high indicators at pre-start trainings, warm-up, and before the start it "breaks down" and shows a significantly lower result. This situation is quite common and is explained low psychological readiness of an athlete, his personality traits and inability to overcome a sports crisis.

According to a number of researchers, in modern society in relation to sports of the highest achievements, a contradictory situation has developed: on the one hand, at most international competitions "Bolshoi Sport" is given a high assessment from the point of view of humanistic values and ideals, and on the other - among a significant part of out and some part of the intelligentsia, there is a "skeptical view of sport", because professional sports form negative dividing people into winners and losers, negates the spirit of cooperation, causes development of personality traits such as egocentrism, aggression, envy, desire to win any at a cost, even at the expense of moral violations etc. [1, 3, 9, 10, 11].

In this regard, the statement of E.A. Litinskaya, who believes that "an important role is played by sports of the highest achievements, the socio-philosophical study of which especially informative from the standpoint of understanding human development as a subject of social progress. This direction of analysis justified from the point of view of reasoned answers to questions such as: is humanity moving towards a balanced development of the individual or towards its ever narrower specialization?

Is civilization evolving towards strengthening human health or its destruction? " [6]. Currently, there are a number

of contradictions in the development of high-performance sports:

- between the growth of sports results high-level athletes (due to the introduction

the latest training technologies; improvement of inventory, equipment, sports

outfits; increasing the volume of training work; the use of the latest pharmacological means of increasing efficiency and recovery of athletes; high economic incentives for competition) and a decrease in the total number of people involved in sports;

- between the humanistic values of sports a social institution and the presence of anti-humanistic sports phenomena (bias and political bias of judges, manifestations of chauvinism, subjectivity and not the friendliness of the fans, severe health disorders of athletes as a result of super-powerful training loads and the use of pharmacological agents, a high degree of commercialization of sports);

- between solving the main problem of mass sports - balanced physical development of a person and, in fact, the merciless exploitation of their physical capabilities in sportsmen in the name of victory at any cost;

- between the increase in the availability of sports for wide sections of the population (by increasing sports facilities, the opening of sections, the emergence and popularization of new sports directions and disciplines - mountain bike, freestyle, workout, etc.) on the one hand, and a reduction in the contingent of potentially capable of achieving high results - on the other [5].

For modern sports of high achievements, the following is characteristic: huge loads, fierce competition, high psychological tension and responsibility. All these the peculiarities of big sports require athlete's specific qualities and special personal properties. In sports psychology, the problem of crises in a sports career has become a priority relatively recently - in the early 90s of the last century. In the works of R.M. Zagainova, N.B. Stambulova, etc. a number of crises in a sports career were highlighted:

1. The crisis of the beginning of sports specialization.
2. The crisis of transition to in-depth training in the chosen sport.
3. The crisis of the transition from mass sports to sports higher achievements.
4. The crisis of transition from youth sports to adult sport.
5. The crisis of transition from amateur sports the highest achievements in professional sports.
6. The crisis of the transition from the climax to the finish line sports career.

In the cognitive sphere of a person, such elements of the structure of consciousness and self-awareness can act as psychological barriers, such as meanings, ideas, knowledge,

etc. In the affective sphere, psychological barriers manifest themselves in the form of emotional experiences and mental states (most often negative), such as anxiety, frustration, fear, etc.

In the behavioral sphere, psychological barriers are expressed in the form of inadequate reduction activity of the subject. B.G. Ananyev was one of the first domestic psychologists noted the role of barriers as psychological formations that give rise to impulses that are significant for the implementation of the initial human activity, while in one case volitional manifestations of activity arise, and in a friend - lack of will. In the process of overcoming psychological barriers, there is a restructuring of the psychological personality structure, is carried out deep internal work to transform the resistance of the environment, the process of meeting the needs of the individual. The most important factor determining the success of overcoming psychological barriers is the subject's creative activity in understanding social status. The main direction of the subject's activity in lines of self-determination coping strategies barriers consists in integration, internal coordination of the semantic sphere, elimination of contradictions, as well as checking the possibilities emerging ways to overcome.

It should be emphasized that psychological barriers “are a kind of psychological reaction of a person to a difficulty that has arisen. Responding to an obstacle is characterized, first of all, by stopping activity during which carries out a special kind of internal work aimed both at experiencing various emotional states and at eliminating the semantic mismatch of consciousness and being, restoring their correspondence and ensuring psychological stability” [2, p. 110].

According to some authors, motivational the basis of high performance sports is self-centeredness. The outside world exists for an athlete as if by himself, surrounding the athlete's own specific world, which is in many ways significantly different from the world is not an athlete: this world has its own special rituals, hymns, clothing, symbols, rules of life and rules of relationships, their values, the main of which is the highest result. For the sake of his athletes make titanic physical efforts, refuse many joys of the “big world”, risk their health, do not realize themselves in any other, unsportsmanlike activity, are ready to cross certain moral boundaries. However, winning records requires unity from an athlete stress of physical and mental strength. By in this regard, F. Shamfle wrote: “Experience has convinced me that to achieve sports greatness needs the body and soul of an athlete to be transformed into one dynamic force” [7].

3. CONCLUSION

The implementation of this requirement depends to a large extent on certain structures of the athlete's personality, especially on its ideological and moral foundations, they determine successful performance in competitions and level of preparation for them, no activities physical, technical and tactical training of the athlete will not be effective, if they do not rely on expedient and purposeful design of the athlete's personality formation.

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